

EVALUATION OF THE EFFICIENCY OF MEASURES AGAINST THE EPIDEMIC IN TREATMENT AND PREVENTION INSTITUTIONS

Akhmedov Avazbek Aliyevich

Fergana public health medical institute, teacher of the department of epidemiology and infectious diseases nursing

Abstract: The article analyzed the issue of evaluating the effectiveness of anti-epidemic measures in treatment and prevention institutions.

Key words: General and private epidemiology, medicine, epidemiology, prevention, virus.

INTRODUCTION

Epidemiology (epidemic and ...ology) is a branch of medicine. He studies the causes and spread of infectious diseases, as well as develops measures to combat and prevent them. Epidemiology is closely related to biology, microbiology, virology, genetics, biochemistry, physics and other sciences. General and private epidemiology are distinguished.

General epidemiology studies the evolutionary basis of the classification of infectious diseases, the epidemic process, categories and laws of epidemiology; private epidemiology studies the unique history, causative agent, epidemiology, source of infection, ways and means of transmission, methods of combating and prevention of each infectious disease.

The history of epidemiology goes back to the distant past. Avesta, the holy book of Zoroastrianism, contains religious and philosophical issues, as well as ideas related to medicine, in particular, the spread of infectious diseases and their prevention.

Attempts to scientifically justify infectious diseases were expressed in the works of Hippocrates, Razi, ibn Sina and others in the Middle Ages. Abu Ali ibn

Sina, in his book "The Laws of Medicine", expressed his thoughts about the main causes of diseases, their triggers, symptoms of diseases and their prevention. It contains information about the invisible causes of several dangerous infectious diseases (cholera, plague, smallpox, tuberculosis, etc.) and their mechanism, as well as the fact that external factors such as polluted water and air play an important role in the occurrence of infectious diseases. described whooping cough. In his works, he was one of the first to think about vaccinating healthy people with liquid from the smallpox (pustula) blisters of patients in order to prevent smallpox. By the 17th century, the English physician E. D. Jenner proposed a smallpox vaccine to treat smallpox. The discoveries of the French scientist L. Pasteur and the German scientist R. Aoch, who proved the role of microbes in the origin of infectious diseases, laid a scientific foundation for the doctrine of immunity. I.I. The researches of Mechnikov and his students, and the work of D. I. Ivanovsky, who first described filterable viruses, became of great importance in epidemiology. As a result of the further development of medicine and health care, significant progress was made in the science and practice of epidemiology. In many countries, including Uzbekistan, a sanitary epidemiology committee was established under the leadership of leading epidemiologists. The development of epidemiology in Uzbekistan is connected with the establishment of the Institute of Epidemiology, Microbiology and Infectious Diseases, the success of major scientists such as L. M. Isayev, P. F. Borovsky, T. Kh. Also, Uzbek scientists A.Z.Zohidov, S.N. Bobojonov, I.Q. Musaboyev and others made a significant contribution to the development of sanitation and epidemiology with their work in the field of epidemiology. In the republic, studies are being conducted on the study of the epidemiology of infectious diseases and the development of measures to prevent them, as well as on the issues of reducing infectious diseases. Currently, a new direction has emerged that studies the emergence, spread and disappearance of epidemic diseases - the epidemiology of

non-communicable diseases. Its main task is to develop prevention methods based on the analysis of data on the etiology and pathogenesis of such diseases and to reduce the number of deaths caused by malignant tumors and other chronic non-infectious diseases among the population.

Methods of measures to prevent infectious diseases and fight against epidemics.

Anti-epidemic measures are a set of measures designed based on the development of modern science and aimed at preventing infectious diseases. Measures aimed at preventing infectious diseases are called preventive measures, and measures aimed at eliminating the epidemic center are called anti-epidemic measures. Such a definition is relative, and in fact, all group activities are aimed at preventing diseases.

Preventive measures require not only the prevention of infectious diseases in the future, but also the reduction of diseases. The measures used in the epicenter of the epidemic include preventive measures, as it is aimed at preventing new diseases in the place where the infectious disease has spread. Various authors use a list of measures against the epidemic, based on its composition, the direction of each of the measures used, and the divided groups. Due to the fact that various anti-epidemic measures are sometimes recommended as part of the epidemic control service, epidemiological diagnostics or epidemic control management are also included in the list of anti-epidemic measures. Thus, the diagnostic directions aimed at the epidemic are as follows: sanitary-epidemiological observations, epidemiological analysis (retrospective and operational), epidemiological investigation conducted at the epicenter of the epidemic, their management, organization of fighting against the epidemic, planning of measures, sanitary and determining the quality of work of epidemiology institutions and specialists. The content and group of anti-epidemic measures are of primary importance. Anti-epidemic measures should be aimed at three factors necessary for the

development of the epidemic process.

List of measures used against the epidemic.

The direction of the group of activities is the source of the disease:

a) diagnosis, isolation, treatment;

b) sanitary-veterinary measures and rodent control. The mechanism of transmission is sanitary and hygienic measures.

Disinfection, sterilization, and disinfection, susceptibility of the organism to diseases, vaccination, immediate vaccination, general laboratory tests, sanitary and educational work, measures to combat certain diseases can be focused on any factor of the epidemic process. and the elimination of any of these factors prevents the further spread of the infectious disease, that is, it leads to the termination of the epidemic center. Measures related to these three factors are as follows:

1) measures aimed at the source of infectious disease agents;

2) measures applied to the transmission mechanism of infectious disease agents;

3) reducing the body's susceptibility to infectious diseases (planned and urgent vaccination).

The measures used in diseases related to the first factor, i.e. diseases specific to the human organism (anthroponosis) and animal organism (zoonosis), which is the source of the infectious disease, are different. The measures used in anthroponosis consist of methods of identifying diseases, isolation of the patient, treatment, and measures such as limiting contact with the surrounding people. In zoonotic diseases, sanitary-veterinary and rodent control (deratization) measures are used.

Indicators for assessing the quality and effectiveness of anti-epidemic measures. Actions aimed at the source of the disease.

The difference between the initial and primary diagnosis of events and

symptoms. Isolation and hospitalization, percentage of isolated (hospitalized) patients compared to total patients, distribution of patients by terms of isolation (hospitalization). Completeness of quarantine and observation places and people. Violation or non-violation of quarantine and observation rules, reduction of the number of rodents in places where deratization was carried out.

Veterinary and sanitary measures The completeness of the implementation of official measures arising from veterinary and sanitary conditions. Measures to cut off the mechanism of transmission of infectious disease agents are carried out based on sanitary and hygienic rules. It is known that they are of great preventive importance. Disinfection, sterilization, and disinsection (measures against insects that spread infectious diseases) are also measures aimed at interrupting the transmission mechanism, and their effectiveness depends on many factors. Measures aimed at the third stage of the epidemic process are preventive vaccination (a separate topic will be devoted to this). The "parasite-causing" and "cannibal" populations that make up the parasitic system are biologically different. This, in turn, causes clinically different diseases and at the same time has a certain effect on the manifestation of the epidemic process. Measures applied to the mechanism of transmission of the disease.

The efficiency indicator of the measures is the completeness of the implementation of the measures indicated in the official documents arising from the sanitary and epidemiological situation of sanitary and hygienic measures directed against the epidemic. The percentage of places where disinfection is carried out compared to the places where it should be carried out. Transfer period (in the case of an infectious disease). The share of the places where disinsection is carried out compared to the places where it is necessary to carry it out. The number of insects in this place before and after disinsection. Activities aimed at the body's susceptibility to diseases. Vaccination and immediate vaccination. The proportion of vaccinated among the population.

Immunological tests among the vaccinated. The time elapsed from the time of exposure to vaccination. The number of vaccinated among those who should be vaccinated. Activities in the general direction: laboratory tests, full inspection of people and places where laboratory tests should be conducted, quality of tests and sanitary education work:

The number of lectures, conversations, documents, visual aids and their compliance with modern sanitary-epidemiological requirements. The second group of factors includes various external environmental conditions, which can increase or decrease the parasitic nature of pathogens, and at the same time, the epidemic process. affects how it manifests. These factors include the natural and social environment, including the living and working conditions of the population, as well as effective anti-epidemic measures. It is necessary to make a true assessment of the role of each natural and social factor in the origin and spread of infectious diseases and to recommend anti-epidemic measures that should be used in specific epidemic conditions based on the factors affecting the internal development of the epidemic process. Such evaluation is based on the results of epidemiological diagnostics. The third sign is used to determine the main direction of the implemented measures, which is their effective result and simplicity in practical application. It should be assumed that the use of the first and second signs indicated above is based on a highly effective result. It is appropriate to apply anti-epidemic measures to all stages of the epidemic process. Several participants participate in the application of some measures. It is necessary to describe five different tasks of epidemic fighters: organizational, diagnostic, methodological, executive and control. In the implementation of some measures, several participants participate in the performance of different tasks. The goal of the modern system of combating epidemics is to drastically reduce infectious diseases among the population and to completely eliminate some of them. The system of combating the epidemic is based on the measures applied

based on the result of the disease detection, scientific manuals aimed at preventing and combating infectious diseases. The public service of the anti-epidemic system should be strengthened on the basis of the law.

According to the health laws of the Republic, the health of the population is ensured through the socio-economic system and medical and sanitary measures. This document also describes the responsibilities of all state agencies, enterprises, institutions and organizations in solving issues related to public health. In accordance with the measures to combat the epidemic, the executive committee of the Council of People's Deputies, hokims, heads of enterprises, institutions, organizations and other leaders should take timely measures to prevent infectious diseases, and actively participate in their elimination when the disease occurs. must do. The group of measures is focused on each factor of the epidemic process, depending on its direction, in which the anti-epidemic agent may or may not be used, and at the same time it should be aimed at preventing the disease.

References

1.Musaboyev E.I., Boyjonov A. K., Yuqumli kasalliklar, epidemiologiya va parazitologiya asoslari, T., 2004 y.

2.Mirtazaev O.M. “Epidemiologiyadan amaliy mashg’ulotlar uchun qo’llanma”. Toshkent 2009 y.

3. Абдуллаев Л.Е. “Эпидемиологиядан амалий кўрсатмалар ” Тошкент 2000 й.